

The History and the Structure of Hospices in Uzbekistan

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Abstract

In the modern world, there is a constant increase in the number of patients suffering from incurable forms of diseases in the terminal stage of development. This trend actualizes the study of palliative care, which is a special area of social and medical care for terminally ill people. Palliative care is an integrated part of cancer patient care. However, the situation in palliative care in Uzbekistan is very critical. Implementing palliative care and hospice into medicine began in 2017 in Tashkent, Uzbekistan. The first Children's Hospice -Taskin was opened in 2022 in Tashkent, Uzbekistan. Despite the fact that 2 years have passed since the opening of the hospice in the Republic of Uzbekistan, the concept of hospice has not yet formed in the minds of the population, there is still an idea that people perceive the concept of "hospice" as a house of death. This article is intended to study the history and structure of palliative care in Uzbekistan and study the perception of hospice among the population.

Introduction

As palliative care began in the 1960s in the UK hospitals, since then it has immediately spread to other countries [1]. The pioneering approach at St Christopher's Hospice, founded in 1967, demonstrated that the principles of hospice care could be applied to other settings. Dr. Cicely Saunders, the founder of the modern hospice movement, proposed the concept of "total pain," emphasizing that it is not enough to relieve only the physical pain of the patient, it is necessary to pay attention to the psychological, social and spiritual components that make up all the pain and suffering of the patient. The term "palliative care" itself was adopted in 1974 in order to highlight this area as an independent discipline of practical medicine. The goal of palliative care is to ensure a decent level of quality of life for such patients and their family members. Traditionally, throughout the world, including in our country, palliative care as an independent direction originated in oncology, since mostly terminal cancer patients are in greater need of relief from pain and unbearable suffering [2,3]. The need for the

development of palliative care throughout the world is confirmed by the Amsterdam Declaration of the Rights of the Patient (1994), the Lisbon Declaration of the Rights of the Patient (1981) and many other international documents, including documents of the Council of Europe, WHO, official guidelines of the European Association for Palliative Care, declarations of professional associations and congresses [2]. For the first time, the definition of palliative medical care is given in the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated April 4, 2017 No. 2866 "On measures to further develop the oncological service and improve oncological care to the population of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2017-2021." In 2022 the first children's hospice -Taskin was constructed in Tashkent.

In 2017 Palliative care was mentioned for the first time in Presidential Decree No. 2866 "On measures for the further development of oncological services and improvement of oncological care for the population of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2017 - 2021". One year later, Palliative treatment departments were created in all branches of the oncology center in Uzbekistan. After

More Information

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that in 2019 Adopted RCM No. 892 “On additional measures for the further development of oncology services and improvement of medical and psychological care for patients with late stages of cancer. Finally in 2022 Hospices were prepared in all regions (with the exception of Tashkent, only a children's hospice operates in Tashkent), protocols for the treatment of chronic pain syndrome, cachexia and palliative treatment of cancer patients were developed.

Methods

In preparation for the establishment and eventual opening of the Hospice, a comprehensive review of relevant laws and regulations was conducted. Additionally, research papers on palliative care and hospice from 2017 to 2024 were thoroughly examined, alongside local and global news coverage and pertinent presidential decisions. In addition, we conducted a survey involving children and their companions who have received or are currently receiving hospice palliative care to assess the quality of these services. Participation in the survey is entirely voluntary and is based on informed consent. The survey was held in July 2024, using data from 2022 till now.

Discussion

For the first time, the definition of palliative medical care is given in the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated April 4, 2017 No. 2866 “On measures to further develop the oncological service and improve oncological care to the population of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2017-2021.” Further mechanisms for the development of palliative and hospice care were prescribed in Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers No. 892 of October 26 “On additional measures for the further development of oncological services and improvement of medical and psychological care for patients with advanced stages of cancer.” In the resolutions, palliative medical care is characterized as a set of measures aimed at to get rid of pain and alleviate other severe manifestations of the disease in order to improve the quality of life of terminally ill citizens [5]. With the adoption of new regulations, new opportunities are opened up for the development of palliative care in the country. Recommendations for the provision of palliative medical care to children have already been launched, however for adults are being prepared [2]. To effectively organize a certain type of medical care, it is necessary to determine its content, purpose and goals, and accordingly, on the basis of this, the contingent of patients to whom this type of care will be determined. According to the resolution, palliative treatment departments have been created in all branches of the Republican Specialized Scientific and Practical Medical Center for Oncology. Thus, a network of 14 palliative treatment departments with a total of 220 beds has been created in Uzbekistan. According to various

sources, even with advanced stages of the disease, with adequate palliative treatment, the patient can live his life without suffering from physical and mental-emotional pain. Therefore, it is worth noting that the indication for hospitalization in these departments are potentially incurable patients who are indicated for palliative chemo-radiation, surgical and symptomatic treatment.

To be admitted to the palliative care department, the patient first undergoes a routine diagnostic examination in the outpatient department of the center. After making a symptomatic incurable diagnosis, if possible, specialized treatment to increase survival and improve quality of life, the patient is sent to the palliative care department. If a curable case is detected, complicated by symptoms (chronic pain syndrome, cachexia, psycho-emotional instability), the patient receives advice from a palliative care specialist and, with his recommendations, is hospitalized in a specialized department. Since this department is not surgical, symptomatic surgical interventions (ostomy, stenting, catheterization, etc.) should be carried out jointly with specialists from the surgical departments. After stabilizing the condition and receiving specialized treatment, the patient is discharged for outpatient treatment with recommendations for symptom control. Since pain is the predominant symptom in cancer patients in the later stages, in accordance with the legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the palliative department must have a cabinet with storage of narcotic and psychotropic drugs. Morphine consumption of 0.04 mg per capita is a direct indication of painful deaths in this country [6].

To increase time spent together with family and friends, emphasis will be placed on treatment in outpatient and home settings. Patients whose symptoms cannot be controlled and corrected outside the hospital and patients whose relatives and friends need a “physical and emotional” break from caring for a seriously ill patient are subject to hospitalization. Hospices will provide drug and non-drug treatment for patients in the terminal stage according to current protocols in order to alleviate the symptoms of the disease. The maximum recommended period of stay (it seems better to write bed days) in a hospice is 10 days, exceptions are agreed with the chief physician of the hospice. After stabilization of symptoms and improvement of general condition, the patient is discharged under observation at home. In the event of a patient's death, relatives are issued a post-mortem epacris and a death certificate without performing a pathoanatomical autopsy.

Another important point in organizing hospice care is the educational component. At the moment, a palliative care training course has been compiled for nurses, bachelors, specialized masters and specialists

who have decided to retrain in palliative care. It is planned to create a course in palliative care at the colleges for training paramedical personnel, oncology departments of the country and at the Tashkent Institute for Advanced Training of Doctors. It is also annually planned to send at least 5 specialists abroad for short- and long-term training at the expense of government and sponsorship funds.

Thus, the creation of a structure for palliative and hospice care will make it possible to minimize the suffering of patients and their loved ones both during treatment and at the end of life. The organization of these institutes will also help improve the turnover of beds in medical institutions, facilitate the work of oncologists and other specialists, directing all their efforts to the treatment of curable cases. Conducting on-the-job training for oncologists and palliative care courses for masters and clinical residents together with the Ministry of Higher and Secondary Special Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan on the basis of oncology departments of higher medical educational institutions and the Tashkent Institute of Postgraduate Medical Education was begun with the teaching aids prepared for the course were included in the Ministry of Health of the Republic of Uzbekistan on January 25, 2020. From 2020 to 2024 an annual team of 5 specialists in the field of palliative care specialists had internships in foreign medical institutions.

Results

Taskin Children's Hospice has been operating since August 2022. In the period from August 2022 to July 2024, 227 patients and 375 visits were registered in the hospice. The number of visits is naturally higher than the number of patients, because the patients applied to the hospice several times. The highest number of visits were once recorded with 10 visits in 2023.

We successfully contacted 103 patients, and 93 agreed to participate in the survey. Out of these 93 respondents, 92 stated that they liked the hospice and that their children's final days were made comfortable. They noted that their children arrived in poor condition but left in good health, having recovered from cancer and now undergoing check-ups every six months. Only 1 patient reported dissatisfaction with the hospice. Of the 93 patients who participated in the survey, 52 are still alive. Among these 52 patients, 3 were admitted for hospice palliative care in 2022, 24 in 2023, and 25 in 2024. Moreover, 10 out of 44 patients have recovered and are currently only undergoing examinations. Of the

41 patients who died, 3% were not related to cancer, they died of infectious disease or simple pneumonia. The parents of patients whose children died also expressed positive opinions about the hospice. They noted that their children spent their last days without difficulty and pain. They expressed their gratitude to the hospice staff.

Since 2022, the hospice has been carrying out charitable actions and volunteer activities. On various holidays, such as New Year, Navroz, Kurban, and Ramadan Eid, volunteers organize various games and a festive table to cheer up children and parents. The activities include body art, making different shapes from plasticine and clay, karaoke, flipping, movie nights, origami, and other entertaining activities. Children's favorite singers also have been visiting the hospice and giving concerts.

Conclusion

In 2017, the Republic of Uzbekistan adopted its first law on the use of palliative care. In 2022, the first children's hospice was launched. By July 2024, 227 patients had received palliative care at the hospice. According to a survey conducted at Taskin Hospice, 98.7 percent of patients had a positive opinion about the facility. They emphasized that Taskin is not a "house of death." Patients highlighted that at the hospice, they not only receive palliative care but also actively fight and overcome their illnesses with the support of staff of Hospice.

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